

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University,
Czech Republic

**Title: SOP for shutting down and turning on the GC
Exploris**

Date: 12.11.2024

Version: version 1

Author: Kateřina Coufalíková

Checked: Akrem Jbebli

Summary

This section describes how to shut down the system for a maintenance or service procedure.

- **IMPORTANT:**
- When turning Off the GC: first turn off the temperature and then turn off the carrier gas flow
- When turning ON the GC: first turn on the carrier gas flow
- For cooling Front/Back Inlet (the one connected to the column), Oven and GC Auxiliary Heaters 1 and 2, don't use > Maintenance > Cool for maintenance. After turning On software will automatically load values from last used instrument method. Before turning off the instrument load instrument method for cooling (cooling before shut down. method) or set the temperatures of Front Inlet, Oven and Heaters 1 and 2 to 20°C then turn off the instrument
- Before turning off move the injector to position 1

To turn off the GC Exploris

1. Load the cooling before shut down method to a sequence in Chromeleon or other Instrument Control Software (XCalibur) and submit the sequence or set the temperatures of the Front inlet, Oven, Auxiliary Heaters 1 & 2 and EI source to 20 ° from the touch screen.
2. Wait until temperatures are (120 - 80°C or lower) ~ 60-90 min (EI source and Auxiliary Heaters 1 & 2).

NOTE: The oven and Front inlet typically cool down very quickly.

3. Turn off the Chromeleon 7 software to **Off mode**

4. Push down the power switch (breaker) to take the Electronics to Servis mode
5. Push down the power switch (breaker) to take the Exploris to Off mode
6. Turn off the computer and unplug the power cable (during a longer power/instrument outage)

7. Turn off the carrier gas flow of the Front/Back inlet (Instrument Control > Front Inlet PTV/Back Inlet SSL > Column flow > Off)

8. Turn off TriPlus RSH autosampler, see Figure 1 and remove the power cable (during a longer power/instrument outage)
9. Move the TriPlus RSH autosampler Head to the position 1 (move arm to edge) see Figure 2

Figure 1 Main power of the TriPlus RSH autosampler

Figure 2. TriPlus RSH autosampler position 1

NOTE: When turning off the autosampler, position 1 (free slot of automatic tool station ATC) is ideal to avoid any collision that could alter functioning of the head or affect the liquid station and syringe. This position will also allow to perform maintenance on the head if needed.

10. Power off the GC: Push down the power switch (breaker), located at the back of the instrument and unplug the power cable from AC Input (during a longer power/instrument outage)
11. Turn off the Nitrogen (cylinder)
12. Turn off the carrier gas Helium (small valve)
13. Turn off the pump and remove the power cable (during a longer power/instrument outage)

To turn on the GC Exploris

1. Plug the power cable from the pump on and turn on the pump
2. Plug the power cable and turn On the computer
3. Turn on the Helium carrier gas
4. Turn on the Nitrogen
5. Plug all power cables from AC Input
6. Push the Main power switch (breaker) to the position On

NOTE: The pumps switch on automatically and the device waits for connection.

Wait 10 minutes for switching pumps to on mode.

7. After **10 minutes** push up the power switch (breaker) to take the electronics of Exploris to **On** mode
8. Power on the GC:
 - a. Plug the power cable to AC Input and push up the power switch (breaker), located at the back of the instrument
9. Power TriPlus RSH autosampler:
 - a. Plug the power cable to AC Input located at the back of the instrument (autosampler) (see Figure 1)
10. **Turn on** the carrier gas flow (0.8 ml/min) of Front inlet/Back inlet (Instrument Control > Front Inlet PTV/Back Inlet SSL > Column flow > On) and wait **10 minutes**. Set ion source, oven and auxiliary heaters temperature using the instrument control system:

11. Go to Chromeleon 7 software > Thermo MS

Tuning > Ion Source > Ion Source Temperature

280 (°C) and oven to 70-80 (°C) and set the

temperature of Auxiliary Heaters 1 and 2 to **150 (°C)** at the same time

NOTE: Set the source temperature to 280 °C quickly because after turning on the device automatically goes into bakeout

NOTE: Check if the gas flow gradually increases and then is constant: No leak in the system

12. Increase the carrier gas flow to **1.2 ml/min** and wait **10 minutes**

13. Set the temperature of Front Inlet PTV/Back Inlet SSL to **80 (°C)** and wait **30 minutes**

NOTE: When the Instrument Status > Vacuum system is Ok – Ultra High vacuum (UHV) enabled

If the Fore Vacuum is at least < 5 mbar and UHV pressure is < 5 x 10⁻⁸ mbar, GC Exploris should go automatically to **Bakeout**

NOTE: If the pressure in the UHV region is higher (above 1E-9 mbar) the instrument must be baked out for at least 10 hours and more, typically 12 hours (plus time for cooling). After Bakeout Ultra High Vacuum should reach at least 8e-10 mbar (ideally up to 7e-11 mbar)

Figure 3 Schematic of vacuum system in Orbitrap Exploris

Method for cooling down instrument before shutting down

Tipless

Step 1 – Wait For Sync Signal (GC)	GC	GC1
Step 2 – Set Output Signal (GC)	GC	GC1
	Signal	Injected

GC-MS method setup

GC Inlets (TRACE 1300/1310)

Liner: Wool PTV, Restek, cat 21117-213.5

O-ring; Thermo Scientific; cat. 29001318

Front Inlet Options	Use this inlet ✓	
	Temperature Settings	
	Enable temperature control	No
	Temperature	No
Inlet Parameters	Operation mode	Split
	Split flow control ✓	
	Split flow	40 ml/min
	Split ration	33
	Purge flow control ✓	

	Purge flow	3 ml/min
	Vacuum compensation ✓	
	Enable gas saver mode ✓	
	Gas Saver Flow	20 ml/min
	Gas saver time	5.00 min
Front Inlet Flow/Pressure Options	Mode	Constant flow at 1.2 ml/min

GC Oven Settings (Trace 1300/1310)

Prep Run Timeout	10 min
Oven equilibration time	0.5 min
Ready delay	0.0 min
Send parameters only (don't run the GC)	✓
Mode	Constant temperature at 20.0 °C

GC Aux Heaters (TRACE1300/1310)

Heater Options	Heater1	Enable	True
		Temperature	20 °C
	Heater2	Enable	True
		Temperature	20 °C

GC (TRACE1300/1310)

Column: Rxi-5Sil MS; 0.25 um, 0.25 mmID; 15m length; Restek; cat. 13620 (use 15 m column)

Post-column: Rxi Guard Column 0.25 mmID; 5 m length; Restek; cat. 10029 (install only 2 m)

Pre-column: Rxi Guard Column; 0.53 mmID, 5 m length; Restek; cat. 10054 (install only 2 m)

Column nut, Self Tightening; Agilent Technologies; cat. 5190-5233

To inlet: Compact Ferrules 0.8 mm (graphite); Restek; cat. 20285

To MS: Ferrules 0.4 mm; 85% Vespel/15% Graphite; Restek; cat. 27071

Kit + connectors, MicroUnion Siltite; 0.25-0.53 ID; Restek;

cat. 23887

Kit + connectors, MicroUnion Siltite, 0.25-0.25 ID; Restek; cat. 23885

FrontColumn	Validate column configuration✓	
-------------	--------------------------------	--

	Length	15.00 m
	Diameter	0.25 mm
	Film thickness	0.25 µm

MSDevice (Orbitrap Exploris GC 240)

Global Parameters

Application Mode	Default		
Method Duration (min)	60		
Internal Mass Calibration	Off		
Ion Source Properties	Filament Power Table	Time (min)	State
	1	0	Off
	2	2	Off
	Use Ion Source Settings from Tune	/	
	Ion Source Temp	20	
	Ionization Mode	EI	
	Calibration Gas	Use From Tune	
	Calibration Gas Level	Use From Tune	
	Filament	Use From Tune	
	Emission Current	Use From Tune	
	Electron Energy	Use From Tune	
	Electron Lens	Use From Tune	
	C-Trap Offset	Use From Tune	
Optics	Use From Tune		

Scan Parameters

Full Scan	Full Scan Properties	Orbitrap Resolution	60 000
		Scan Range (m/z)	70-700
		AGC Target	Custom
		Normalized AGC Target (%)	100
		Maximum Injection Time Mode	Auto
		Microscans	1
		Data Type	Profile
		Polarity	Positive

System

Run Time	60 min
----------	--------

